

The evolution of food safety risk communication: Models and trends in the past and the future

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ABSTRACT

Management of risks and uncertainty played an important role in the rise of human cultures from the beginning. Long journey has been taken from deciphering spiritual signs to the usage of artificial intelligence. Communication about risks also went through an evolutionary path and became highly specialised. During previous decades, food safety risk communication developed to be a distinguishable and well-grounded profession. Based on literature of the last 40 years, the evolution of food safety risk communication is presented from the perspectives of consumer involvement, methodological approach, and challenges. Expected future trends are also unfolded during the analysis. The paper identifies 5 + 1 stages in the evolution of food safety risk communication: Pre-risk communication era, Deficit model, Dialogue model, Partnership model, and Behavioural insight model. Expected future trends are summarised as a 6th stage, called Controlled risk environment model. The models are separated by level of consumer involvement and methodological approach. Consumer science played a crucial role in the evolutionary procedure. Despite the observed advancement between the stages, the application of each communication model might have justification under certain circumstances. In practice, the different stages have no clear boundaries, and the models can overlap. An organisation can even move on to the next phase by skipping a previous evolutionary step.

1. Introduction

Evaluation of risks and uncertainty has played an important role during the evolution of human cultures from the beginnings (Covello & Mumpower, 1985). A long journey has been taken since deciphering spiritual signs until the usage of mathematical models and artificial intelligence for analysing risks. In parallel, the communication about risks also went through an evolutionary path. Scientists had to explain new kinds of risks, new scientific approaches and had to deal with the increase of public interest, anxiety and mistrust (Plough & Krimsky, 1987). As the probability theory and statistical methods used for risk assessment have developed, risk communication principles also went through significant changes. New approaches and tools were implemented for mediation of risk-related information towards the public and later for translation of scientific knowledge for consumers, then raising awareness and modifying consumer attitudes (Nowotny et al., 2005). During the past decades, taking behavioural biases into account is playing an important role in risk communication as well.

Besides methodological progression, the areas of risk communication

also started to be separated and became highly specialised (Starr & Whipple, 1984). For instance, these days risk communication in financial investments and public health share only few basic elements and require rather different competences. During the previous decades, risk communication in food safety also developed to be a distinguishable and well-grounded profession (Renn, 2009; EFSA, 2021).

Food safety risk communication approaches and methods – especially regarding consumer engagement – changed over time following the development of social science, going through well-distinguishable stages. Some studies can be found to deal with the shift from one stage to another (Lewenstein, 2003; Qiu et al., 2016), delivering important observations about the limitations of a certain risk communication model and the historical necessity of the transition. Some pioneering papers also presented a broader framework that integrated the shifts between the particular stages and indicated that these transitions are parts of an evolutionary process in risk communication (Chess, 2001; Covello & Sandman, 2001; Fischhoff, 1995; Trench, 2008), however the timeframe of these studies usually lasts until the early 2000s, and only few of them deals with the pre-risk communication era (Covello &

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Mumpower, 1985; Covello & Sandman, 2001; Qiu et al., 2016). Another common limitation of the studies about the evolution of risk communication that they often have a generalized thematical focus (Fischhoff, 1995; Gurabardhi et al., 2005; Lewenstein; 2003; Qiu et al., 2016), thus their observations are less relevant to the food safety field. Finally, to the best knowledge of the authors, no previous studies can be found about the expectations of future trends of food safety risk communication.

This study aims to fill the identified gaps and provide a coherent concept for the evolution of modern era food safety risk communication of authorities, discussed and interpreted across five stages, focusing on the level of consumer involvement, the methodological approach, and the challenges of the different courses. The expected future trends are considered as the sixth step.

2. Eras of food safety risk communication

2.1. The pre-risk communication era – Rule of technocrats (before the 1980s)

Risk analysis appeared institutionally only in the 18th century as a function of the emerging modern states protecting their citizens with centrally organized public service systems. Expert-driven risk analysis became dominant in the late 1940s when a variety of quantitative methodologies (operations research, system analysis) were introduced (Plough & Krimsky, 1987). Scientists then were able to establish a rational, evidence-based background to support governmental decision-making for risk management and communication.

In the beginning, risk communication primarily meant crisis management, focusing on minimising organizational risks in crisis situations (Heath & O’Hair, 2010; Sheppard et al., 2012). In this period systematic preventative risk communication did not exist, moreover, risk-related information exchange between the public and the risk managers was entirely out of the scope. Public authorities were obliged to protect consumer health by legislations and authority measures, and food safety was considered as a purely technological challenge. An example of this approach is the Morinaga Milk brand’s arsenic contamination case in Japan, in 1955. During this incident, the public announcement about the identified toxic substance in the milk formula and the withdrawal issued by the government were made more than two weeks after the causative agent was found. Meanwhile, several surmising articles have appeared about what makes dozens of babies sick in the media. Following the public announcement, panic erupted, and hospitals flooded with those concerned about their children (Ui, 1992). The literature specifies this stage as pre-risk communication, in which the public was ignored during the whole process of risk management (Qiu et al., 2016), as long as the risk could be maintained at a tolerable level (Fischhoff, 1995; Covello & Sandman, 2001). Fischhoff (1995) also points out that the public had become accustomed to the lack of information they received.

2.2. The Deficit model – We know better what you need (the 1980s)

During the 1980s, our human risk-related knowledge developed quickly (Gurabardhi et al., 2004). Especially chemical hazards such as pesticide residues, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, mycotoxins, dioxin contamination alarmed risk managers who understood the food chain concept (Moriarty, 1984; Dallinger et al., 1987) and the challenges caused by long-lasting exposure, bio-accumulation and delayed and chronic effects. In this era, the food sector also became highly industrialised and globalised, therefore physical actions (plant and product inspections) taken by local authorities seemed to lose efficiency in managing risks. These recognitions motivated food safety decision-makers to analyse and adopt some basic risk communication principles and methods that had been already applied in other sectors, especially in the public health and hazardous industries (Starr & Whipple, 1984; Heath & O’Hair, 2010; Qiu et al., 2016) to empower the society to manage risks. This intention met with public demand for an

increased flow of risk-related information (Krimsky & Golding, 1992; Covello & Sandman, 2001), fuelled by media reports of the contemporary scientific findings in the field of foodborne illnesses (Frewer, 2004). Still, risk managers of this era considered that citizens lack the competence to understand the scientific and technological background of the legislation and interventions, consequently incapable of contributing to risk mitigation any other way than following experts’ instructions. An important presumption of the Deficit model is that consumers feel stronger sympathy for interventions that they have factual information about (Lewenstein, 2003), so this consideration determined the goal of the communication. As a response to growing distrust of the society towards science and experts, initiatives were also started to narrow the gap – the “deficit” – between citizen and expert knowledge via education and disclosing of scientific results (Lewenstein, 2003; Groffman et al., 2010; Ahteensuu, 2012). As a new term, public understanding of science (PUS) was coined by the Bodmer report (Bodmer, 1986). The communication of food safety authorities followed a one-way direction (Courchamp et al., 2017; Trench, 2008) and was restrained to factual data and indications to consumers about avoiding crisis situations.

At this point of the risk communication evolution, food safety experts realised that risk-related data must be shared with media representatives too, as media can act as a bridge between consumers and experts (Dickson, 2005; Nisbet & Scheufele, 2009; Ahteensuu, 2012). However, except actual crisis situations, risk management institutions were characterised by a relatively passive media presence, and during crisis events, journalists tended to thematise the flow of discourses. In this age, traditional one-way communication technologies were applied (Gurabardhi et al., 2005), such as press releases, fact sheets, open days and media events, delivering a slight level of public participation.

The BSE (Bovine spongiform encephalopathy, also known as “mad cow disease”) scandal was an important cornerstone for the failure of the Deficit model in 1995. BSE is a prion-mediated, fatal neurological disease with an incubation period of several years in cattle. Its human form, called vCJD (variant Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease), is also causing lethal illness. BSE was recognized first in the 1980s in the United Kingdom, but the risk of transmission to humans was considered low for a long time by the UK government. Independent research institutes, scientists, other countries’ governments, the public and the media estimated the risk as more significant. In addition, the symptoms were appalling, which led to fear of beef consumption even outside the UK, where no cattle or beef batches were exported otherwise (Frewer et al., 2007). The communication of the authorities mainly aimed to avoid panic and protect economic interests (Lanska, 1998). Besides failures in risk management, the lack of responsible risk communication also contributed to the food safety crisis that was big enough to ignite a series of food safety legislation and authority reform around the globe (Kasza, 2006; Vos, 2000). Instead of considering the risk perception of the certain segments of the society and explaining the background of the epidemic and the nature of the uncertainty authorities mostly reported factual data and denied likely correlations between the human and animal cases for a long time. Besides the economic losses, the credibility of the authorities and public institutions has been also severely damaged by the series of questionable governmental actions and contradictory information surrounding the BSE epidemic (Bánáti, 2011; Hansen, 2010).

These events foreshadowed that filling the knowledge deficit (“educating” the public) might be a meaningful endeavour to establish a fluent dialogue with consumers (Dickson, 2005), but far from being enough to preserve or regain public confidence (Sato, 2010). The failure of the Deficit model facilitated the recognition that public risk perception must be a key factor that should be explored and analysed, in order to understand public attitudes towards different risk-related topics (Frewer et al., 2009). As a consequence, several ambitious scientific research programmes have started to explore consumer risk perception in the light of new experiences, following the path of the pioneers of this field in the mid-1980s (Slovic et al., 1982; Wildavsky & Dake, 1990; Fischhoff et al., 1993; Weber & Milliman, 1997; Sjöberg, 1998; Hansen

et al., 2003).

2.3. The dialogue model – Inviting consumers to the table (the mid-1990s)

The Deficit model did not solve the problem of public mistrust in the scientific community (Löfstedt, 2004), as the consumers were still passive audience in the process of risk communication. Food safety related information arrived in form of negative news, as articulated by the media. Educational initiatives for filling the knowledge deficit between experts and consumers arose problems because consumers perceive risk-related information to be insignificant unless they perceive an actual context to their own lives (Fessenden-Raden et al., 1987; Frewer, 2004).

A new paradigm appeared that called for public involvement and the transformation of risk communication to be a bilateral procedure. The so-called Dialogue model (also mentioned as the “Public Engagement in Science” - PES model) of risk communication, therefore concentrated on consultation with consumers. The aim of the communication activities in this stage was extended to gathering information from the society. Representatives of civil organisations were invited for disputes, consumers were asked to participate in focus groups and surveys (Rowe & Frewer, 2005). This model emphasised the importance of public engagement and can be considered as a significant step towards public participation (Regan et al., 2016), although the involvement level was not complete. Both initiation and thematization of the risk-related dialogues were in the hand of risk managers and scientists, focusing exclusively on the topics considered necessary by the experts (Rowe & Frewer, 2005; Trench, 2008).

Despite the Dialogue model being far more ‘conscious’ in the chosen communication techniques than the Deficit model, the efficiency of information dissemination has not resulted in establishing a genuine dialogue between risk managers and the public (Covello & Sandman, 2001; Rowe & Frewer, 2005; Trench, 2008). A genuine dialogue would assume that both parties have the opportunity to initiate a conversation about an issue of interest. Additionally, decisions in a genuine dialogue, in most cases are reached through iterative modifications of the standing points of the participants until a mutually acceptable decision. However, for scientists and policy-makers, the experience of letting laypeople close to decisions was still very new and seemed to pose a real risk of losing control. Also, conversations with the public needed profoundly different communication skills compared to what professionals had at that time (Schneider & Snieder, 2011). On the opposite side, representatives of civil organisations sometimes were not aware of the full consequences of the decision options (Bier, 2001), because they were admitted into dialogue only at a certain point (or a few certain points) in the process while being already frustrated by the lack of the right to take initiatives. Still, the involvement of the public proved to be a more adequate approach for closing the gap between the understanding of citizens and experts (Covello & Sandman, 2001), which was the basic principle of the Dialogue model. The concept was carried on by the Partnership model (the next risk communication model) although with some significant modifications.

2.4. The Partnership model – From now on, we do this together (the late 1990s to the 2010s)

Public participation includes public consultation, involvement and information procedures that are designed for gathering input for decision-making from those who will be affected by the decision as Rowe and Frewer (2000) defined. In this manner, the Dialogue model has gone through several modifications between the 1990s and 2010s for a more organic and immerse public participation, leading to a more consensually accepted model. The phrase “Partnership model” is introduced by the present study for the differentiation of the advanced version of the Dialogue model, referring to Fischhoff’s work (1995). The Partnership model builds on a significant change in the approach to

public involvement, based on a genuine interest of experts in understanding consumer attitudes, motivations, perceptions and behavioural patterns. At this stage in the evolution of risk communication, public participation activities aimed to reach out towards socially robust knowledge that is established by a regime of pluralistic expertise as Nowotny formulates (2003). Many innovative involvement techniques were used to democratize risk communication, such as citizens’ juries, panels, consensus or search conferences, deliberative opinion polling and study groups (Lewenstein, 2003; Rowe & Frewer, 2005). Besides consultative platforms, consumer research programmes also helped decision-makers to explore these factors (Frewer, 2004; Redmond & Griffith, 2004; Verbeke et al., 2007).

Food safety authorities at this level of development started to pay special attention to collecting consumer feedback and experiences, using them as soft signs that often forecast high risk situations or indicate need for better measures. The Partnership model inherently assumes that even a lay consumer might deliver ideas and experiences that help experts and the authority to manage risks, therefore the lay public must be involved in risk assessment and management (Fischhoff, 1995; Qiu et al., 2016). Public participation also contributes to the perception of transparency and building trust of consumers (Lewenstein, 2003; Rowe & Frewer, 2000). The main differences between the Dialogue- and the Partnership-model are presented in Table 1.

Risk perception studies explored that consumers tend to significantly underestimate some risks while overestimate others, based on their previous experiences (Frewer et al., 2009; Tiozzo et al., 2011). Several factors influence human risk perception, which must be implemented in effective risk communication activities (Breakwell, 2000; Charlebois & Summan, 2015). Fischhoff et al. (1978) identified nine attributes of risk which has significantly affect consumer risk perception: voluntariness, immediacy, known by exposed, known to science, controllability, novelty, chronic or catastrophic nature of the risk, common or dread nature of the risk and severity of the consequences. The inappropriate consumer judgement of general and extraordinary risks poses a serious risk to society. The results of risk perception studies allowed experts to launch novel educational programs and preventive communication campaigns specifically designed for the mitigation of certain risks (Griffith et al., 1998). In the Partnership model, a new series of research appeared to explore the area-specific risk perception biases (Charlebois & Summan, 2015; Nielsen et al., 2009; Olsen et al., 2010) considered by risk communicators and managers.

The Partnership model fosters a more proactive communication than the previous models, emphasizing the importance of institutionalised risk communication. In this era, risk communication specialists and dedicated risk communication units appeared in the authorities. This structural change is a significant difference between the Partnership model and the previous models (Qiu et al., 2016).

The weakness of the model is that – similarly to the previous risk communication models – it aims to alter, moreover “fix” consumer behaviour, attitudes and awareness. Public participation models assume some active awareness on behalf of consumers, which can be a good basis for knowledge development and attitude shifting. The Partnership model does not take the limitations and conditions of the human learning process into accounts, such as information overload, selective attention and the false application of the acquired knowledge (Süth et al., 2018; Scholderer & Veflen, 2019). This might be the reason why the impact of risk communication campaigns fell short of expectations in changing consumer risk perception (Hansen et al., 2003; Jacob, Mathiasen, & Powell, 2010), as these activities are more likely to reach those segments of the society, who have already been more aware of the specific topic (Verbeke et al., 2007). Besides all of the mentioned pitfalls, evaluating the effectiveness of food safety communication campaigns tends to be also difficult. Changes in knowledge, awareness and attitude are easily measurable indicators in consumer surveys, although these indicators do not reflect actual behaviour and practices in real households because of some resilient psychological factors such as the

Table 1
Differences between the Dialogue model and the Partnership model.

Differences	Dialogue model	Partnership model	References
Who can initiate a conversation?	Risk managers	All stakeholders	Rowe and Frewer (2000) Covello and Sandman (2001) Löfstedt (2004) Rowe and Frewer (2005) Qiu et al., 2016
When do the consumers become involved?	At certain points according to the decision by risk managers	Consumers are involved from the beginning and the procedure remains transparent for all stakeholders	Rowe and Frewer (2000) Frewer (2004) Rowe and Frewer (2005) Qiu et al., 2016
The level of consumer involvement	Periodic, limited to certain topics, constrained by methodology	Continuous, non-limited areas, innovative methods to establish genuine participation	Rowe and Frewer (2000) Rowe and Frewer (2005) Trench (2008) Qiu et al., 2016
Novel factors in decision-making	Consumer risk perception becomes a factor	Risk-benefit perception, research on risk perception biases	Fischhoff (1995) Bier (2001) Chess (2001) Covello and Sandman (2001) Frewer (2004) Rowe and Frewer (2000) Bier (2001) Löfstedt (2004) Rowe and Frewer (2005)
Novel tools and methods	Basic public participatory techniques, introduction of consumer research	Innovative public participatory methods such as citizens' juries, panels, consensus conferences, deliberative opinion polling and study groups, continuous consumer studies (including time series), also stakeholder research	Rowe and Frewer (2000) Bier (2001) Löfstedt (2004) Rowe and Frewer (2005)

optimistic bias and the attitude-behaviour gap (Redmond & Griffith, 2004; Moreaux et al., 2018). One example could be the study of Tiozzo et al. (2011) analysing a food safety campaign on salmonellosis prevention in Veneto region of Italy. Their pilot campaign reached more than 50,000 households in 2007 with flyers sharing information on the characteristics of the bacteria, symptoms of the illness and practices for avoiding the infection. From the aspect of education, the campaign was a success: the knowledge of consumers who read the information was significantly higher than the others (Tiozzo et al., 2011). However, despite the proven knowledge-related achievement of the risk communication action, the number of reported salmonellosis cases per year stagnated between the years 2007–2009 in the region (Russo et al., 2017).

The usually low impact of awareness-raising and educative risk

communication campaigns demonstrated the need for a novel perspective in risk communication, which is not based on forcing a change in consumer behaviour without observation of actual patterns and understanding their roots (Redmond & Griffith, 2003).

2.5. The Behavioural insight model – If you can't change, live with it! (from the 2010s)

Until the 2010s, food safety-related policy-making considered the rational consumer behaviour as an alignment point, ignoring the limitation of human capabilities concerning coherent risk understanding and consistent behaviour. Over time, it became apparent that cognitive biases are embodied in behavioural biases, making attitude changes hardly predictable when analysed as a function of education and awareness-raising attempts (Niedermeier & Ariely, 2009). The increasing demand for understanding the motivation underlying consumer actions and decision-making processes gave green light to a novel approach in research. The emergence of behavioural insight originated from analysing consumer attitudes towards tax compliance. Research studies proved that human behaviour (modelled with the intention to pay taxes and debts) is strongly influenced by human nature and social environment (Arcos Holzinger & Biddle, 2016). Behavioural sciences attempt to analyse human behaviour through observational studies (Straßheim & Beck, 2019), based on empirical findings to identify the underlying reasons behind the investigated behavioural pattern.

Integration of behavioural insight into policy/technology/process design is based on “changing people's behaviour without changing their minds” (Troussard & van Bavel, 2018). Behavioural insight is an approach which combines psychology and social science with empirical observations in order to understand the reasons for human decisions in a new dimension (Kuehnhans, 2019). Applying behavioural insight elements in policy-making is a promising contemporary ideology in the evolution of risk communication. It has an outstanding role in identifying and understanding the biased consumer routines and misbeliefs. Then, during the implementation stage, the policy instruments can also be designed with behavioural insights. Based on the conceptualized human actions and daily routines, easily-applicable solutions can be developed and integrated into consumer lifestyle, without altering ingrained habits, following the theory of practice that allows the inspection of human routines from a social science perspective (Halkier et al., 2011). This requires a profound change in the working method of the authority. Besides bilateral communication, surveys and focus groups, an effort has to be made for receiving real-life impressions about consumer behaviour. Good examples of this could be seen during the COVID-19 pandemic, when some food safety authorities surveyed the population for mapping their perceptions of the measures, fears about the food safety-related aspects of the epidemic, and explore consumer behaviour in a quarantine situation. BfR (Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung), the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment launched a survey-series called the “BfR-Corona-Monitor”, in which 500 randomly selected people, representing the German population was interviewed via telephone every week (BfR, 2020). This monitoring program started in March 2020, and the results are published continuously on the institute's website and social media pages. Nébih (Nemzeti Élelmiszerlánc-biztonsági Hivatal), the Hungarian national food safety authority, analysed consumer practices regarding stockpiling and food waste besides food safety concerns through two annual surveys entitled as “quarantine questionnaires” (Nébih, 2020 and 2021). In 2020, the representative sample size was 3000, while in 2021, 1910 people participated in the online survey. The results and the advice based on the findings were communicated on several online platforms, also through traditional channels such as television and radio.

Carefully planned and ethically sound observational studies also have to be organized that reveal routines of shopping, food transporting, storage, cooking, eating, handling the leftovers, operating the refrigerator, cleaning the utensils and taking care of personal hygiene. The

analysis of these “consumer journey” studies along with a risk ranking process, will reveal the actual risky behaviours to be targeted in the risk communication.

Besides a more precise targeting, the deeper understanding of consumer behaviour opens new horizons in risk mitigation practices also (Skuland, 2020; Ueland, 2019). In parallel with the progression of gamification (Koch et al., 2022), the application of creative media tools (infographics, short videos, interactive applications, personalised tools) is also emerging, helping the aiming of specific consumer groups (Crovato et al., 2016).

2.6. Controlled risk environment model – Technology mediated risk communication era (future trends)

According to the future of risk communication, not much can be found in the recent literature. However, by observing the trends of developments in the borderline of communication and technology, it might be assumed that several intelligent technological assistant agents will surround the consumer (installed in the environment, worn on the body or implanted) within a few decades, weaving an almost undetectable net of safety (Bostrom, 2003; Wogalter, 2006). This assistant technology, or more likely a network of technologies could formulate situation-dependent messages based on miniaturised sensors. These technologies may cover rapid analytical tools for contaminant detection and product traceability validating applications, and online connection to risk-related databases and risk assessment algorithms with alerting functions. The databases and algorithms are framed by human experts but maintained and optimised by artificial intelligence. The personalised assistance (probably using augmented reality tools at least in part) and the tangible practical benefits of the safety network around the individual would ensure that the messages on food safety risks reach even those consumers who are less efficiently reached by traditional risk communication methods or might be sceptical to accept advice. This individual-centred network (controlled risk environment) would greatly increase the effectiveness of risk mitigation; additionally, these in-home and on-person technologies can also support the optimisation of nutrition and help sustainable consumption (for instance, by decreasing food waste due to consumer habits). Indicators of the effectiveness will be based likely on health burden effects in regard to food safety risk mitigation and optimised nutrition.

In this era, traditional risk communication is expected to be replaced by personalised services for the most part, placing the consumer in a controlled risk environment. However, some of the previous models might remain in use in some situations, in which they had been already proven to be effective. Food control authorities will likely keep the role of supervising the food chain safety system to enforce business activities to remain within legal and ethical boundaries, and besides regulatory work they will also take part in scientific research and development for optimising new technologies.

3. Discussion and conclusions

In the evolution of the applied risk communication models in food safety, each stage represents a higher level of consumer engagement and a better understanding of consumer behaviour. In this sequence, the different models build on each other, completing or replacing some of the characteristics of the previous ones.

The development of risk communication does not have a defined timeline, as the different stages have no clear boundaries, and the periods can overlap. An organisation can even move on to the next phase by skipping a previous evolutionary stage (Chess, 2001). The evolutionary process must be interpreted within the framework of a given country or organisation.

Although some studies argue that the above-mentioned transformation processes in risk communication practice cannot be interpreted as evolution or hierarchy (Trench, 2008), several evolutionary

trends can be observed from the Pre-risk communication era through the Dialogue-, Deficit- and Partnership models to the Behavioural insight. The scope of risk communication activities has expanded: from minimising the devastating effect of a specific crisis to general awareness-raising and later on observing daily routines and understanding the psychological aspects of certain food risk related situations. Simultaneously, the target group of the different risk communication activities has become more specific and aimed, based on the revealed consumer knowledge, habits and behaviour. Characteristics of each stage, such as attributes of the communication methods, applied tools, focus of research, and the problematic points which triggered the next evolutionary step are summarised on Fig. 1. All eras are presented in the order of the first appearance in the history of food safety risk communication.

The application of each risk communication model (despite the observed evolutionary stages) might have justification under certain risk communication circumstances (Suldovsky, 2016), considering the type of the risk, consumer knowledge and attitudes. The strengths and limitations of each model are summarised in Table 2. There is also a strong indication that the Deficit model will be persistent in the field of risk communication for several more decades (Ahteensuu, 2012; Simis et al., 2016), as it has inescapably ingrained in decision-making.

3.1. Limitations

This study focuses on food safety risk communication models and their evolution in the last decades, which also indicates its limitations. The statements of this work might not be applicable in other professional fields of risk communication. Communication methods, channels, the formulation of messages and measurement of efficiency were not in the scope of the analysis.

The perspective of the academic literature on risk communication models reflects primarily the viewpoint of authorities. This work follows the same path. While risk communication could be important for companies also, they mostly deal with crisis communication, and only a marginal importance is attached to preventive risk communication. Non-governmental organisations might have an important function in risk communication, however – apart from a few exceptions – they do not pursue this activity in a systematic way, and only a few long-lasting programmes could be identified. Authorities play a crucial role in both crisis communication and preventive risk communication, and are expected to continually improve their preparedness in these fields.

Outlook on the future of food safety risk communication is barely conceptualized in the scientific literature, therefore the predictions in this chapter mainly reflect on the expectations of the authors based on impressions about the development of risk communication models and technological advancements.

3.2. Policy implications

This study delivers potential benefit to decision makers in the field of food chain control. There is a diversity of applied models in the practice of food safety authorities. Institutions can be found in different development level in this regard. Some of them rely on advanced consumer research activities and seek opportunities for integrating behavioural insights into their risk communication activities, while others barely moved past the Deficit model. Understanding of the evolutionary path paved by the described models could help the development of current approaches.

3.3. Research implications

The clear distinction of the risk communication models and the description of their innovative aspects and limitations might inspire the development of further methodological approaches. Apart from the Pre-risk communication era, all of the risk communication models were

Fig. 1. The evolutionary stages of food safety risk communication.

Table 2
Strengths and limitations of the different risk communication models (after the Pre-risk communication era).

Risk communication models	Strengths	Limitations
Deficit model	Straightforward messages The approach does not require organizational changes or strong communication competencies	Does not build trust No influence on behaviour
Dialogue model	Bilateral communication Involvement of the public and gaining credibility Transparency	Effectiveness is low Reach of consumers is low
Partnership model	Focuses on topics which really matters to consumers Good for educational purposes Builds trust Gathers consumer data	Requires interdisciplinary approach Does not consider limitations of human learning process Forces to fix consumer behaviour without of understanding the roots Forces to change consumer preferences (which is extremely difficult) Effectiveness is low
Behavioural insight model	Takes consumer routines and preferences into consideration Provides solutions that doesn't force consumers to change ingrained habits or preferences	Requires intensive interdisciplinary research and development collaboration Understanding actual consumer behaviour requires resources from the organisation Officers have to understand a completely new and different approach
Controlled risk environment model	Overrides the problem of human inattention and disinterest Does not require special efforts from the consumers Constant adaptation and optimisation	Linked to technological progress Requires very intensive collaboration between several professional fields (transdisciplinary approach)

fostered by contemporary multidisciplinary research, indicating the role of scientists in the evolution of the models.

The Behavioural insight model currently poses several challenges for practitioners of food safety risk communication. There is a considerable need of scientific input for tailoring risk mitigation advice to actual behavioural patterns.

Declarations of interest

None.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Gyula Kasza: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Eszter Csenki:** Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Dávid Szakos:** Writing – review & editing. **Tekla Izsó:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration.

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